

THE PHOSPHOMOLYBDIC ACID-TOCOPHEROL COLOUR COMPLEX

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The reaction of phosphomolybdic acid with tocopherol (vitamin-E) has been investigated and the resultant complex studied. The blue complex was isolated in solid form and a preliminary study conducted on the nature of the complex formation. Based on experimental evidence, a tentative mode of formation has been proposed, suggesting the condensation of phosphomolybdic acid with tocopherol in the molecular ratio of 1:2.

Most of the colour reactions of the tocopherols, described by previous workers (Emmerie and Engel, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1938, 67; 351; Furter and Meyer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1939, 22, 240; Schulek and Roxsa, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1943, 126, 253; Kofler, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1945, 28, 702), have utilised oxidation-reduction systems. Weisler *et al.* (*Anal. Chem.*, 1947, 19, 906) coupled the individual tocopherols with *o*-dianisidine dihydrochloride, and Quaife (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1948, 175, 605) chromatographed the nitroso derivatives through zinc-carbonate-celite column. We studied the development of the P.M.A. (phosphomolybdic acid)-tocopherol colour reaction which was utilised for the estimation of vitamin-E (Nair and Magar, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1954, 42, 577). In the present work, the P.M.A.-tocopherol complex has been isolated in the solid form and its chemical nature studied. The characteristics of the complex have been investigated and its chemical constitution tentatively arrived at.

EXPERIMENTAL

The phosphomolybdic acid-tocopherol complex was prepared as follows: To phosphomolybdic acid (B.D.H.-Analar, 3.94 g.), dissolved in 20 c.c. of pure glacial acetic acid (Mercks. G.R.) and pure *dl*- α -tocopherol (Roche, 0.86 g.), dissolved in 20 c.c. of glacial acetic acid, was gradually added with constant stirring. The whole solution was kept at 0° overnight and then distilled at about 39°/1 mm. The dark compound left in the distillation flask was dissolved in a small quantity of alcohol and filtered through glass-wool. The thick viscous liquid was concentrated in vacuum (over conc. H₂SO₄ and P₂O₅) to a dry solid. Complex formation did not take place when *dl*- α -tocopherol was substituted by its esters.

Characteristics of the Complex.—The compound is a dark blue solid, possessing a peculiar aroma, characteristic of esters. It decomposed at 240° during melting in the capillary tube.

The solid complex was found to decompose slightly on keeping exposed to air, yellow crusts of phosphomolybdic acid being formed on the surface. A dehydrating atmosphere such as that in a vacuum desiccator containing H₂SO₄ and P₂O₅ was found to aid in the preservation of the complex.

It is highly soluble in ethyl alcohol, acetonitrile, isopropyl alcohol, ethyl acetate, methyl formate, and fairly soluble in other fat solvents like ether and benzene. The solubility in water is fairly good, but on keeping the complex decomposes, releasing phosphomolybdic acid.

Effect of p_H on the Formation of the Complex.—Experiments were conducted with phosphomolybdic acid solution in acetic acid-alcohol in different proportions at various p_H values, using different concentrations of acetic acid, keeping, however, the concentration of P.M.A. the same. α -Tocopherol (Roche) was taken in 1 c.c. aliquots of ethyl alcohol and to it 2 c.c. of P.M.A. solution was added, and the amount of complex formed noted by measurement of the colour intensity in a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter, after 5 minutes. Measurements of p_H were made with a Beckman Model G p_H -meter at 28°. It is evident from the results (cf. Fig. 1) that the formation of the complex is possible only in highly acid medium, best being glacial acetic acid itself.

Spectrophotometric Studies.—Spectrophotometric measurements and determination of molar ratio of the phosphomolybdic-tocopherol complex were carried out. All measurements were made with a Beckman Model DU quartz spectrophotometer, with corex absorption cells of 1 cm. width. The visible absorption spectra gave maxima at 490 $m\mu$ and 725 $m\mu$ (Nair and Magar, *loc. cit.*). The $E_{1\%}^{1\text{cm}}$ at 725 $m\mu$ in ethyl alcohol was 23.3, whereas for pure phosphomolybdic acid it was 0.038. As the complex showed a high $E_{1\%}^{1\text{cm}}$ at 725 $m\mu$, optical density measurements were made at 725 $m\mu$ on the P.M.A.-tocopherol reaction. In each set of reaction, the P.M.A. concentration was gradually increased (0.0002 to 0.004 M), keeping the concentration of tocopherol constant (0.002 M). The molar equivalents in the reaction are shown in Fig. 2 for a fixed concentration of tocopherol (0.002 M). This provides data suggesting the presence of two molecular complexes, the first in the ratio 1:1 and the second, 1:2. The curve shows 'plateau formation' corresponding to 0.001 M and 0.002 M of P.M.A., indicating complex formation in 1:2 and 1:1 molar proportions.

FIG. 1

Effect of p_H on complex formation.

FIG. 2

Influence of p_H and conc. on absorbance at 725 $m\mu$.

The nature of the tocopherol moiety in the complex not being known, a study of the infra-red spectrum was resorted to. Because of the possibility of a change in

constitution, involving the rupture of the heterocyclic chroman ring, and the resultant formation of a *p*-quinone, our study of the infra-red region was limited to around 1650\AA . Also, a complete examination of the absorption spectra in the infra-red region was extremely difficult since no single suitable solvent open for investigation in the entire range of the infra-red spectrum was available.

The infra-red spectra were taken on a Leitz infra-red spectrophotometer using acetonitrile as a solvent. Though the infra-red spectral study of quinones is relatively unexplored, available data lead us to expect a strong C=O stretching vibration band in the region near about $1650\text{-}1690\text{ cm.}^{-1}$ which is not indicated in the present substance. Thus, in all probability, the tocopherol moiety remains intact during complex formation.

DISCUSSION

The present reaction from the experimental evidence indicates a direct complex formation, hitherto unknown. The P.M.A.-tocopherol reaction proceeds in the forward direction only in a purely glacial acetic acid medium. The presence of water or alcohol or any solvent containing moisture has been found to suppress the reaction, and this is primarily in favour of suggesting the formation of a complex by the elimination of water. Previous literature (Karrer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1939, 22, 334) shows that oxidimetric reactions are capable of taking place in any solvent.

It is well known that molybdenum affords a group of blue compounds, apparently resembling our present substance, and loosely called as 'Molybdenum blue'. The phosphomolybdic acid-tocopherol colour complex, isolated by us, possesses characteristics which are markedly different from the substances designated as 'Molybdenum blue'.

Moreover, the existence of a Werner type complex of molybdic acid with oxalates and resembling 'Molybdenum blue' has been already established (Barbieri and Malaguti, *Mem. Accad. Sci. ist. Bologna*, 1951-52, 9, 3). Here the formation of a blue Werner complex with oxalates could have been easily mistaken for the 'Molybdenum blue' obtained by previous workers wherein only Mo, oxygen and H_2O form the constituents of the molecule. Although oxalic acid is a well-known reducing agent, we have, in course of the work, evidence to show that molybdic acids do form complex molecules in association with organic compounds.

The mechanism of the P.M.A.-tocopherol colour reaction has to be explained as an elimination of H_2O molecules between the polarised $:\text{C}(\text{OH})$ groups of the tocopherol molecule and the $-\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ part of P.M.A. This is considered to be so because highly dehydrating conditions aid in the formation of the complex, and presence of moisture leads to its slow decomposition. The fact that esters of α -tocopherol do not react with P.M.A. to provide the complex is in further support of this interpretation. The spectrophotometric observations indicate the presence of two complexes in the molar ratios 1:1 and 1:2. The complex formation may take place by two molecules of tocopherol condensing with the $2\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ part of one molecule of P.M.A., the condensation being complete in two successive stages. Furthermore, in marking this observation it was found that the complex obtained showed stability only at very low p_{H} values, a fact not met with in the inorganic salt of P.M.A.

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